

Basics of Research Data Management

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EIRENE'S KICK-OFF MEETING, 2nd March 2018, Ljubljana

Content

- 1) Who we are and what we do
- 2) Reserch Data Management
- 3) Open questions and dilemmas

Social Science Data Archives, University of Ljubljana

<http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- 1997
- National data repository for social sciences
- Depositors from all 4 (3 public) universities, private research centres, Statistical Office of Slovenia (8-10 research centres per year)
- 600 social science surveys
- cca. 700 users yearly (90 % education, 10 % scientific/research purpose)
- Member of [CESSDA ERIC](#)
- [International projects](#) (DwB, Foster, SEEDS, SaW, SERISS ...)

ADP's mission

The ADP is a national infrastructure that collects important data sources from a wide range of social sciences, interesting for analyzing the Slovenian society, deposits, preserves and promotes their further use in scientific, educational and other purposes.

🏠 USE DATA 📄 DEPOSIT STUDY 🖨️ LEARN ABOUT

HOW TO GET DATA?

FIND →

REGISTER

→ ANALYZE

HOW TO DEPOSIT DATA?

RECORD →

PREPARE

→ DEPOSIT

<https://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

Deposit your data with ADP →

Archiving with trusted domain repository

- archiving with the help of an expert will enhance data quality
- expert help is most likely to be available at a trusted domain repository and an institutional repository.

In 2017 ADP gained

ADP Social Science Data Archives
<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/eng/>
CTS Certification 2017-2019

LEARNING HOW TO ARCHIVE DATA

Social Science Data Archives, University of Ljubljana

- Search and find more than 600 social science surveys [on-line](#)

CESSDA Topic Classification

CERIF Topic Classification

- DEMOGRAPHY, POPULATION, VITAL STATISTICS AND CENSUSES
- ECONOMICS
- EDUCATION
- HEALTH
- HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
- INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
- LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
- LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
- NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
- Not categorized
- OTHER
- POLITICS
- PSYCHOLOGY
- SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
- SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPINGS
- SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
- SOCIETY AND CULTURE
- TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
- TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY

The oldest dating in 1962

Study description in Slovenian and English

Studies about Slovenia and the ones Slovenian researchers are involved in

https://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/vsebinska_podrocja/

@CESSDA countries, 2017

- Austria
- Belgium
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Hungary
- Netherlands
- Norway
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Sweden
- Switzerland (Observer)
- UK

CESSDA training group

- New on-line expert tour guide on **Research Data Management** for researchers was launched on December 14, 2017 in Ljubljana
- Prepared by 17 CESSDA SPs
- ADP leading a chapter „Archive & Publish“
- Workshops planned for 2018 →
 - a) for researchers: 11th April 2018 in Ljubljana
 - b) train the trainer: 12th and 13th April in Ljubljana

Expert tour guide on Data Management

You will be guided by European experts who are - on a daily basis - busy ensuring long-term access to valuable social science datasets, available for discovery and reuse at one of the [17 CESSDA social science data archives](#). With this guide and the training events being held across Europe, we want to accompany and inspire you in your journey through the research data life cycle.

Target audience and mission

This tour guide was written for social science researchers who are in an early stage of practising research data management. With this tour guide, CESSDA wants to contribute to increased professionalism in data management and to improving the value of research data.

The [Expert Tour Guide on Data Management](#) by CESSDA ERIC

Data Management Plan

A good data management strategy takes into account:

- technical,
- organisational,
- structural,
- legal,
- ethical and
- sustainability aspects.

The time invested in setting up a good data management strategy pays off when the time comes to reproduce your analysis and results.

The [Expert Tour Guide on Data Management](#) by CESSDA ERIC

Data Management Plan

... offers added value in the following ways:

The [Expert Tour Guide on Data Management](#) by CESSDA ERIC

Research Data Lifecycle

The [Expert Tour Guide on Data Management](#) by CESSDA ERIC

Let's dive into...

Adapt your Data Management Plan

A list of Data Management Questions based on the
Expert Tour Guide on Data Management

You can [view and download it](#) (CESSDA, 2017)

What ADP will ask from you at the end...

To be able to understand your data →

- 1) Sampling procedures
- 2) A questionnaire // Questionnaires
- 3) Consent form // forms
- 4) Instructions for interviewers
- 5) Instructions for coding
- 6) Instructions for...
- 7) Reports
- 8) Data

[Link](#) to a „Study discription“ form at ADP!

DMP – on line tools

<https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk>

[Home](#)

[About](#)

[Future plans](#)

[Help](#)

[Change language](#) ▾

Welcome.

DMPonline helps you to create, review, and share data management plans that meet institutional and funder requirements. It has been jointly developed by the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) and the University of California Curation Center (UC3).

Sign in

[Forgot your password?](#)

<https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>

Data Publication

PUBLICATIONS AND DATA

It is expected that a Data Publication will ensure that data will potentially be considered as a first-class research output (Knowledge Exchange, 2013).

For a dataset to “count” as a publication should be:

- Properly documented with metadata;
- **Reviewed for quality;**
- Searchable and discoverable in catalogues (or databases);
- Citable in articles.

How to publish research data?

Self-archiving

- without any help
- a quick and easy way to publish data
- check: [Dryad](#), [Figshare](#), [Zenodo](#)...

Archiving with trusted domain repository

- archiving with the help of an expert will enhance data quality
- expert help is most likely to be available at a trusted domain repository and an institutional repository.
- Check: [CESSDA ERIC SP](#)

LEARNING How To ARCHIVE DATA

For more information see soon: *CESSDA Expert tour guide on Data Management (on-line module) to be launched in December 2017 on CESSDA ERIC web-site!*

Thank you!!!

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